

Orbits with constant velocity on bodies of
rotation shells

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Chapter 1

The frictionless case

In a body of rotation is a ball.

A shell rotates, then a ball on the shell moves to a higher position. There are several questions. Is the ball in balance in this situation or does the ball fall down? Is there a free play? Are there areas in which the ball cannot stay? It's clear that the rotation velocity of the shell plays a major role in this situation. What is with other quantities? Which dependences are from this quantities? Are there quantities from which the situation is independent? The situation of a rotating shell is physical equivalent to a circling ball on a motionless shell. In all chapters the radius of the ball is very small compared to the measurements of the body of rotation. We want to determine the dependence from r and v (velocity) and the angular velocity ω , too. Gravitation and centrifugal force must be in balance. The centrifugal force often acts in everyday life. Everybody knows of the centrifugal force for example at a round-about or driving a curve.

1.1 The general revolution solid

We view a shell of a general revolution solid. The angle of inclination of the inclined plane is α .

m = mass of the small interior ball

g = gravitation acceleration

F_z = falling force

Z_z = centrifugal force against the falling force

$$F_z = mg \sin \alpha \quad \text{and} \quad Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha$$

see the following figures:

F_N, Z_N are normal forces.

It follows:

$$Z_z = Z \cdot \cos \alpha \quad Z_N = Z \cdot \sin \alpha$$

we obtain:

$$Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha \quad \alpha = \gamma$$

Now we look at the shell of a general body of rotation.

$h(r)$ is the function of the body of rotation.

$$h'(r) = s = \tan \alpha = \text{slope}$$

α is the angle of inclination. We obtain:

$$F_z = mg \cdot \sin \alpha \quad Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha$$

It is valid:

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha}} \quad \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha} = \tan \alpha$$

With this it follows:

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{\tan \alpha}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha}}$$

Now we insert s and we get:

$$F_z = \frac{mgs}{\sqrt{1 + s^2}} \quad Z_z = \frac{mv^2}{r\sqrt{1 + s^2}}$$

For a stable orbit it must be again $F_z = Z_z$ (balance), with that:

$$\frac{mv^2}{r\sqrt{1 + s^2}} = \frac{mgs}{\sqrt{1 + s^2}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad v^2 = g \cdot r \cdot s$$

With that it follows:

$$v = +\sqrt{g \cdot r \cdot s}$$

For the angular velocity we get:

$$w = \frac{v}{r} = \sqrt{\frac{g \cdot s}{r^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{g \cdot s}{r}}$$

Because of $s = h'(r)$ a transformation from v or w to r isn't possible in general. This must be done with a given function $h(r)$.

If the barycenter is in the midpoint of the ball, we can do the following.

R is the radius of the ball.

For the angle δ it is valid: $\delta = 180^\circ - 90^\circ - (90^\circ - \alpha) = \alpha$ With the figure we obtain:

$$r_m = r \cdot \frac{r - R \cdot \sin \delta}{r}$$

With $\tan \alpha = s$ and $\sin \delta = \frac{\tan \delta}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \delta}}$ we conclude:

$$r_m = r \cdot \frac{r - \frac{R \cdot s}{\sqrt{1 + s^2}}}{r} \quad (1.1)$$

with $s = h'(r)$

With a small ball r_m is less smaller than r .

If we insert r_m instead of r into the equations, we get the angular velocity and the velocity at the barycenter of the ball. We assume that the small ball has a (local) constant density. This is valid to all chapters. The exact calculation with barycenter we get the barycenter's velocity (small ball):

$$v_m = \sqrt{g \cdot r_m \cdot h'(r)}$$

Angular velocity:

$$w = \frac{v_m}{r_m} = \sqrt{\frac{g \cdot h'(r)}{r_m}}$$

With

$$v = v_m \cdot \frac{r}{r_m}$$

we obtain the velocity at the point of contact.

The rotation body's function $h(r)$ is always the interior one. Wir define:

$r = r_i =$ interior radius

$r_a =$ exterior radius

$h(r)$ must have only **one** touching point with the ball. With that no “troughs” with two touching points see figure:

From the general body of rotation we can derive different special cases.

1.2 Cone of rotation

Now we view a cone of rotation:

$\alpha =$ apex angle of the cone

Because of the figure we recognize:

$$h(r) = \frac{r}{\tan \alpha} \quad \Rightarrow \quad s = h'(r) = \frac{1}{\tan \alpha}$$

If we insert in the general formula $v = \sqrt{gr s}$ for $h(r)$ and s , we get the velocity:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{g \cdot r}{\tan \alpha}}$$

Transformed to r :

$$r = \frac{v^2 \cdot \tan \alpha}{g}$$

We obtain the angular velocity:

$$w = \frac{v}{r} = \sqrt{\frac{gr}{\tan \alpha \cdot r^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{g}{r \cdot \tan \alpha}}$$

Transformed to r again:

$$r = \frac{g}{w^2 \cdot \tan \alpha}$$

See Sommerfeld [3], §14.1, p.73.

Because of the using of equation (1.1) we calculate now $\frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}}$.

$$\frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} = \frac{1}{\tan \alpha \cdot \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{\tan^2 \alpha}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tan^2 \alpha + 1}} = \cos \alpha$$

With equation (1.1) it follows:

$$r_m = r \cdot \frac{r - R \cdot \cos \alpha}{r}$$

The consideration of barycenter leads to:

$$v_m = \sqrt{\frac{g \cdot r_m}{\tan \alpha}} \quad w = \sqrt{\frac{g}{r_m \cdot \tan \alpha}} \quad v = v_m \cdot \frac{r}{r_m}$$

1.3 Ellipsoid of revolution

We now treat the ellipsoid of revolution. The semi-axis a is on the x-axis and on the y-axis, the semi-axis b on the z-axis. The z-axis shall be axis of rotation. The semi-axes a and b can be arbitrary.

The canonical equation of the ellipse is:

$$\frac{r^2}{a^2} + \frac{h^2}{b^2} = 1$$

Transformed:

$$h^2 = b^2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{a^2}\right) = b^2 \cdot \frac{a^2 - r^2}{a^2}$$

With this we follow:

$$h(r) = \pm \frac{b}{a} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}$$

Differentiation to r :

$$s = h'(r) = \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{-2r}{\pm \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}} = \pm \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}$$

With $v = +\sqrt{gr}$ follows:

$$v = +\sqrt{g \cdot r \cdot \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}}$$

at last:

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{b \cdot g}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}} \quad (1.2)$$

The angular velocity w can be written as:

$$w = \frac{v}{r} = \sqrt{\frac{bg}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}} \quad (1.3)$$

Approximation for $r \ll a$:

$$v \approx \frac{r}{a} \cdot \sqrt{bg} \quad w = \frac{v}{r} \approx \frac{1}{a} \cdot \sqrt{bg}$$

Now we must search the relation between r and r_m . In the case of the ellipsoid of revolution we get for the expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} &= \frac{br}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{b^2 r^2}{a^2 \cdot (a^2 - r^2)}}} \\ &= \frac{br}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2 + \frac{b^2 r^2}{a^2}}} = \frac{br}{\sqrt{a^4 - r^2 a^2 + b^2 r^2}} \end{aligned}$$

We insert this term in equation (1.1):

$$\begin{aligned} r_m &= r \cdot \frac{r - \frac{brR}{\sqrt{a^4 - r^2 a^2 + b^2 r^2}}}{r} \\ r_m &= r \left(1 - \frac{bR}{\sqrt{a^4 - r^2 a^2 + b^2 r^2}}\right) \quad (1.4) \end{aligned}$$

With barycenter's correction we get:

$$v_m = r_m \cdot \sqrt{\frac{b \cdot g}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}} \quad v = v_m \cdot \frac{r}{r_m}$$

The angular velocity is the same.

1.4 A ball as special case of the ellipsoid of revolution:

It is possible to treat the ball as special case of the ellipsoid of revolution with the ball's radius $R_k = a = b$, too. With specialization of the formulas (1.2) and (1.3) we get:

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{\sqrt{R_k^2 - r^2}}} \quad w = \sqrt{\frac{g}{\sqrt{R_k^2 - r^2}}}$$

Approximation for $r \ll R_k$:

$$v \approx r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{R_k}} \quad w \approx \sqrt{\frac{g}{R_k}}$$

Specialization of (5):

$$r_m = r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R}{R_k}\right)$$

A calculation with barycenter yields:

$$v_m = r_m \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{\sqrt{R_k^2 - r^2}}} \quad v = v_m \cdot \frac{r}{r_m}$$

The angular velocity remains unchanged.

1.5 Paraboloid

We now turn to the paraboloid of revolution. For the parabola it is valid:

$$x^2 = 2py$$

We look at the following figure:

Notations:

$$\text{focal length } f = \frac{p}{2} \quad x = r, y = h$$

$$r^2 := 2h \cdot 2f = 4hf$$

With this we obtain:

$$h := \frac{r^2}{4f} \quad s := h'(r) = \frac{r}{2f}$$

With $v = +\sqrt{gr \cdot s}$ follows:

$$v = \sqrt{gr \cdot \frac{r}{2f}} = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{2f}}$$

For the angular velocity:

$$w := \frac{v}{r} = \sqrt{\frac{g}{2f}}$$

w is independent of r .

We transform the velocity equation to:

$$r = v \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2f}{g}}$$

To the relation between r and r_m :

$$\frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} = \frac{r}{2f \cdot \sqrt{1 + \frac{r^2}{4f^2}}} = \frac{r}{\sqrt{4f^2 + r^2}}$$

With equation (1.1) we get:

$$r_m = r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R}{\sqrt{4f^2 + r^2}} \right)$$

A calculation with the small ball's barycenter leads to:

$$v_m = r_m \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{2f}} \quad v = v_m \cdot \frac{r}{r_m}$$

The angular velocity remains unchanged.

1.6 Hyperboloid

We now view the orbit on the hyperboloid of revolution's shell:

Canonical equation of the hyperbola:

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$$

Wise are the notations:

$$y = r, x = h$$

We insert in the canonical equation:

$$\frac{h^2}{a^2} - \frac{r^2}{b^2} = 1$$

Transformed

$$h^2 = a^2 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{b^2}\right) = \frac{a^2}{b^2} \cdot (b^2 + r^2)$$

with that:

$$h = \frac{a}{b} \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}$$

The slope s can be calculated as

$$s = h'(r) = \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{2r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}} = \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}$$

With $v = +\sqrt{gr s}$ follows:

$$v = \sqrt{gr \cdot \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}} = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{ag}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}} \quad (1.5)$$

One approximation for $a, b \ll r$:

$$v \approx r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{ag}{br}} = \sqrt{\frac{arg}{b}}$$

asymptote: $h'(r) \approx \frac{a}{b}$

angular velocity:

$$w = \frac{v}{r} = \sqrt{\frac{ag}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}}$$

for $a, b \ll r$:

$$w \approx \sqrt{\frac{ag}{br}}$$

Now we determine the ball's midpoint velocity:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} &= \frac{ar}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2+r^2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+\frac{a^2 r^2}{b^2 \cdot (b^2+r^2)}}} \\ &= \frac{ar}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2+r^2+\frac{a^2 r^2}{b^2}}} = \frac{ra}{\sqrt{b^4+r^2 b^2+a^2 r^2}} \end{aligned}$$

From (1.1) we conclude:

$$r_m = r \cdot \frac{r - \frac{Rra}{\sqrt{b^4+r^2 b^2+r^2 a^2}}}{r}$$

at last:

$$r_m = r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{Ra}{\sqrt{b^4+r^2 b^2+r^2 a^2}} \right)$$

With this barycenter's correction we get:

$$v_m = r_m \cdot \sqrt{\frac{a \cdot g}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2+r^2}}} \quad v = v_m \cdot \frac{r}{r_m}$$

The angular velocity is the same.

Generalizations:

a): Instead shell of rotation bodies we can view an arm that has got the form of the rotation body.

This arm rotates and the body is in balance between gravitation and centrifugal force. If the body glides frictionless, the same equations are valid. (We especially

achieve this with rotation bodies as balls, cylinder.)

b): The frictionless case in medium can be treated in the same way, if we insert instead of g , $\frac{g(\rho_K - \varphi_F)}{\varphi_K} = g \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\rho_K}\right)$ (see for example Budo [2] §16 p.85) in the equations. φ_F is the medium's density (liquid or gas) and φ_K is the body's density that is in balance (not the density of the rotation body's shell).

reasons:

There are only gravitation and centrifugal force in this balance case. The centrifugal force is independent from medium, in the orbit case the centrifugal force is only dependent from r and v , we can see it in the derivation of the centrifugal force, but not from medium. The gravitation acceleration changes from g to $g \cdot \frac{\rho_K - \varphi_F}{\varphi_K}$. Only with the gravitation there is a change, because of this we can insert $g \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_F}{\rho_K}\right)$ instead of g .

In the case $\varphi_F > \varphi_K$ the rotation body's shell (respectively the arm) must be turned round, instead of

then

Then the same equations are valid again.

Chapter 2

The friction case

We introduce the following notations:

m = mass of the ball
 R = radius of the ball
 g = gravitation acceleration
 F_R = friction force
 μ = general friction coefficient
 μ_H = static friction coefficient
 μ_G = sliding friction coefficient
 μ' = rolling friction coefficient
 α = angle of inclination of the plane

We explain the factor δ in the following way:

$$\delta = \begin{cases} \frac{5}{7} & \text{if } \frac{\mu'}{R} < \mu_H \text{ (rolling)} \\ 1 & \text{if } \mu_H < \frac{\mu'}{R} \text{ (sliding)} \\ \frac{5}{7} \text{ or } 1 & \text{if } \frac{\mu'}{R} = \mu_H \neq 0 \text{ (decision is open)} \\ 1 & \text{if } 0 = \frac{\mu'}{R} = \mu_H \text{ (frictionless)} \end{cases}$$

See Assmann [1], volume 1, chapter 11.10, p. 265.

The acceleration b on the inclined plane is:
 $b = \delta g \cdot \sin \alpha$, the velocity v and the distance s are $v = \delta g \sin \alpha \cdot t$ and $s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \delta g \cdot t^2 \cdot \sin \alpha$.

If a ball is rolling on the inclined plane, it is $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$ see for example Budo [2], §57, p.302, equation (8). The moment of inertia J of a ball is $J = \frac{2}{5} \cdot mR^2$. The

general formula for rolling on the inclined plane can be written as:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}} \quad (2.1)$$

One derivation can be found at * (at the end of the chapter) or we can see this with Budo [2], §57, p.302, equations (5)-(7). With the moment of inertia of the ball we get:

$$b = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{2}{5}m} = \frac{5}{7} \cdot g \sin \alpha \quad (2.2)$$

Then we get in the case of rolling $\delta = \frac{5}{7}$.

The forces are (see fig.):

$$F = mg \sin \alpha \quad F_N = mg \cos \alpha$$

friction force

$$F_R = \mu \cdot F_N = mg \mu \cos \alpha$$

In the friction case is:

$$\mu = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu'}{R} & \text{if } \mu_H > \frac{\mu'}{R} \text{ (rolling)} \\ \mu_G & \text{if } \frac{\mu'}{R} > \mu_H \text{ (sliding)} \\ \mu_G \text{ or } \frac{\mu'}{R} & \text{if } \mu_H = \frac{\mu'}{R} \text{ (decision is open)} \end{cases}$$

See Assmann [1], volume 1, chapter 11.10, p.265. In the case of friction is:

$$F = mg \cdot (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha) \quad b = g \cdot (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha)$$

$$v = gt \cdot (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha) \quad s = \frac{1}{2} \cdot gt^2 (\delta \sin \alpha - \mu \cos \alpha)$$

If we consider orbits on rotation bodies shells and Z is the centrifugal force, the inequality of stable orbits are see Sommerfeld [3], volume 1, §14.1, p.73:

$$Z_z - F_z \leq Z_R + F_R \quad F_z - Z_z \leq Z_R + F_R$$

with:

$$F_z = \delta mg \sin \alpha \quad F_R = mg \cos \alpha \cdot \mu$$

To the centrifugal forces (see fig.):

$Z = \frac{mv^2}{r} = \text{centrifugal force}$

$$Z_N = Z \cdot \sin \alpha \quad Z_z = \delta \cdot \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \cos \alpha$$

$Z_R = \text{friction force of the centrifugal force}$

$$Z_R = \mu \cdot Z_N = \mu \cdot \frac{mv^2}{r} \cdot \sin \alpha$$

2.1 The orbit on the general rotation body's shell

$h(r)$ = function of the rotation body see figure, $s = h'(r)$.

$h(r)$ has got only **one** touching point with the ball. With that there is no "trough".

We always mention the function of the rotation body the one of the interior shell.

r = interior radius

The following is valid:

$$s = \tan \alpha \quad \cos \alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} \quad \sin \alpha = \frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}}$$

It follows:

$$F_z = \delta mg \cdot \frac{s}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} \quad F_R = \frac{mg\mu}{\sqrt{1+s^2}}$$

$$Z_z = \delta \cdot \frac{mv^2}{r \cdot \sqrt{1+s^2}} \quad Z_R = \frac{\mu mv^2 s}{r \cdot \sqrt{1+s^2}}$$

limit conditions:

$$Z_z - F_z = Z_R + F_R \quad F_z - Z_z = Z_R + F_R$$

Now we use the first equation.

$$\frac{\delta mv_{max}^2}{r \cdot \sqrt{1+s^2}} - \frac{\delta mgs}{\sqrt{1+s^2}} = \frac{\mu mv_{max}^2 s}{r \cdot \sqrt{1+s^2}} + \frac{mg\mu}{\sqrt{1+s^2}}$$

simplified:

$$\frac{v_{max}^2 \cdot \delta}{r} - \frac{v_{max}^2 \cdot \mu s}{r} = g\mu + \delta g s$$

$$\frac{v_{max}^2}{r} \cdot (\delta - \mu s) = g \cdot (\mu + \delta s)$$

at last:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta s + \mu)}{\delta - \mu s}}$$

On the same way we can derive a formula of the minimum velocity with the equation (4). This formula is:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta s - \mu)}{\mu s + \delta}}$$

We here have one s_{max} and one s_{min} that can be calculated with the equations of maximum velocity and minimum velocity.

$v_{max} = \infty$ if $\delta - \mu s = 0$ it follows:

$$s_{max} = \frac{\delta}{\mu} \quad (2.3)$$

$v_{min} = 0$ if $\delta s - \mu = 0$ we obtain:

$$s_{min} = \frac{\mu}{\delta} \quad (2.4)$$

We find:

$$s_{min} \cdot s_{max} = 1$$

In the frictionless case with $\mu = 0$ we get:

$$v_{max} = v_{min} = \sqrt{grs}$$

This formula is the same as the one in chapter 1.

The relation between r and r_m is the same as in chapter 1.

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{r}$

We can derive from the general body of rotation different special cases.

2.2 The cone of revolution

In this case we have:

$$h(r) = \frac{r}{\tan \alpha} \quad s = h'(r) = \frac{1}{\tan \alpha}$$

α = apex angle of the cone

We insert in the formula of the maximum velocity of the general rotation body:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta s + \mu)}{\delta - \mu s}} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot \left(\frac{\delta}{\tan \alpha} + \mu\right)}{\delta - \frac{\mu}{\tan \alpha}}}$$

at last:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta + \tan \alpha \cdot \mu)}{\delta \tan \alpha - \mu}}$$

In the same way we get from the minimum velocity formula of the general rotation body the minimum velocity of the cone of revolution:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta - \mu \tan \alpha)}{\mu + \delta \tan \alpha}}$$

From the general limit conditions $s_{max} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$ and $s_{min} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$ we follow $\frac{1}{\tan \alpha_{max}} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$ and $\frac{1}{\tan \alpha_{min}} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$, on this way we obtain:

$$\tan \alpha_{max} = \frac{\mu}{\delta} \quad \tan \alpha_{min} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$$

At the cone of revolution there are no r_{min}, r_{max} but it exists α_{min} and α_{max} . If we insert $\mu = 0$ in both velocity formulas, we get the formula $v = \sqrt{\frac{rg}{\tan \alpha}}$ for the frictionless case. We know this formula from the chapter before. The relation between r and r_m is the same as in the chapter before with the frictionless case.

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{r}$

2.3 The ellipsoid of revolution

We look at the figure:

From the canonical equation of the ellipse with the semi-axis a, b we get (see the chapter before, too): $b =$ axis of revolution

$$h(r) = \pm \frac{b}{a} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2} \quad s = h'(r) = \pm \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}$$

We again use the formula of the maximum velocity of the general rotation body:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta s + \mu)}{\delta - \mu s}} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot \left(\delta \cdot \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{a^2 - r^2}} + \mu \right)}{\delta - \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{\mu r}{\sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}}}$$

at last:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta br + \mu a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2})}{\delta a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2} - b\mu r}}$$

In the same way we can derive from the formula of the minimum velocity of the general rotation body the following equation:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta br - \mu a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2})}{\mu br + \delta a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}}$$

With the general limit conditions $s_{max} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$ and $s_{min} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$ we get the special conditions of the ellipsoid of revolution:

$$\frac{\delta}{\mu} = \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{r_{max}}{\sqrt{a^2 - r_{max}^2}} \quad \frac{\mu}{\delta} = \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{r_{min}}{\sqrt{a^2 - r_{min}^2}}$$

Now, we transform to r_{max} :

$$\delta^2 a^2 \cdot (a^2 - r_{max}^2) = \mu^2 b^2 r_{max}^2$$

$$\delta^2 a^4 - \delta^2 a^2 r_{max}^2 = \mu^2 b^2 r_{max}^2$$

$$r_{max}^2 = \frac{\delta^2 a^4}{\mu^2 b^2 + \delta^2 a^2}$$

with that:

$$r_{max} = \frac{\delta a^2}{\sqrt{\mu^2 b^2 + \delta^2 a^2}} < a$$

The other limit condition can be transformed to r_{min} in the same way:

$$r_{min} = \frac{a^2 \mu}{\sqrt{b^2 \delta^2 + a^2 \mu^2}} < a$$

For $\mu \ll 1$ it follows now:

$$r_{min} \approx \frac{a^2 \mu}{b \delta} \quad r_{max} \approx a$$

Insertion of $\mu = 0$ in the formulas of maximum and minimum velocity leads to the known formula for the frictionless case (see chapter 1):

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{gb}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}}$$

The equation between r and r_m is the same as in chapter 1.

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{r}$

2.4 Special case ball ($a = b = R_K$)

With specializing the equations of the ellipsoid of revolution we obtain the equations of the ball in dependence from r and not from the height angle. With $a = b = R_K$ we get:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta r + \mu \cdot \sqrt{R_K^2 - r^2})}{\delta \cdot \sqrt{R_K^2 - r^2} - \mu r}}$$

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta r - \mu \cdot \sqrt{R_K^2 - r^2})}{\mu r + \delta \cdot \sqrt{R_K^2 - r^2}}}$$

$$r_{max} = \frac{\delta \cdot R_K}{\sqrt{\mu^2 + \delta^2}} \quad r_{min} = \frac{R_K \cdot \mu}{\sqrt{\delta^2 + \mu^2}}$$

For $\mu \ll 1$ is $r_{min} \approx \frac{R_K \cdot \mu}{\delta}$ and $r_{max} \approx R_K$. For the frictionless case $\mu = 0$ we get with the velocity formulas the known formula

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{\sqrt{R_K^2 - r^2}}}$$

from chapter 1 again.

The relation between r and r_m is the same as in chapter 1.

$$\text{angular velocity} = \omega = \frac{v}{r}$$

2.5 The paraboloid

Now we use the equations of the general rotation body to the paraboloid of revolution. f is the focal distance of the paraboloid.

For the paraboloid is valid see chapter 1:

$$h(r) = \frac{r^2}{4f} \quad s = h'(r) = \frac{r}{2f}$$

Now we insert the parabola function to the formula of the maximum velocity of the general rotation body.

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta s + \mu)}{\delta - \mu s}} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot \left(\delta \cdot \frac{r}{2f} + \mu\right)}{\delta - \frac{\mu r}{2f}}}$$

With that it follows:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta r + 2f\mu)}{2f\delta - \mu r}}$$

In the same way we get from the minimum velocity formula the minimum velocity of the paraboloid:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta r - 2f\mu)}{\mu r + 2f\delta}}$$

From the general limit condition $s_{max} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$ and $s_{min} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$ we obtain with insertion to s :

$$\frac{r_{max}}{2f} = \frac{\delta}{\mu} \quad \text{with that:} \quad r_{max} = 2 \cdot \frac{\delta f}{\mu}$$

and

$$\frac{r_{min}}{2f} = \frac{\mu}{\delta} \quad \text{with that:} \quad r_{min} = 2 \cdot \frac{f\mu}{\delta}$$

In the case $\mu = 0$ we get with the help of the velocity formulas the known formula for the frictionless case (chapter 1):

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{g}{2f}}$$

The equation between r and r_m is the same as in chapter 1.

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{r}$

2.6 The hyperboloid

Under consideration of the figure and the canonical equation of the hyperbola we obtain as in chapter 1: $a, b =$ semi axes

$$h(r) = \frac{a}{b} \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2} \quad s = h'(r) = \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}$$

If we insert the hyperbola equation in the formula of the maximum velocity (general rotation body), we get:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta s + \mu)}{\delta - \mu s}} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot \left(\delta \cdot \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}} + \mu \right)}{\delta - \frac{\mu r a}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}}}$$

with that:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta ar + \mu b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2})}{\delta b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2} - \mu ra}}$$

In the same way we can conclude with the minimum velocity formula of the rotation body:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta ar - \mu b \sqrt{b^2 + r^2})}{\mu ar + \delta b \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}}$$

If $b \ll r$, we can follow:

$$s = h(r) = \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}} \approx \frac{a}{b}$$

Now it follows for $b \ll r$:

$$v_{max} \approx \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta \cdot \frac{a}{b} + \mu)}{\delta - \frac{\mu a}{b}}} = \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta a + \mu b)}{\delta b - \mu a}}$$

With the minimum velocity formula we can calculate in the same way in the case $b \ll r$:

$$v_{min} \approx \sqrt{\frac{rg \cdot (\delta a - \mu b)}{\mu a + \delta b}}$$

If we insert the formula of s into the general limit conditions $s_{max} = \frac{\delta}{\mu}$ and $s_{min} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$, we now get:

$$\frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r_{max}}{\sqrt{b^2 + r_{max}^2}} = \frac{\delta}{\mu} \quad \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r_{min}}{\sqrt{b^2 + r_{min}^2}} = \frac{\mu}{\delta}$$

We transform the first equation:

$$a^2 \mu^2 r_{max}^2 = \delta^2 \cdot (b^2 + r_{max}^2) \cdot b^2$$

$$a^2 \mu^2 r_{max}^2 = \delta^2 b^4 + \delta^2 b^2 r_{max}^2$$

$$r_{max}^2 = \frac{\delta^2 b^4}{a^2 \mu^2 - \delta^2 b^2}$$

at last:

$$r_{max} = \frac{\delta b^2}{\sqrt{a^2 \mu^2 - \delta^2 b^2}}$$

From the equation of r_{min} with a similar calculation we obtain:

$$r_{min} = \frac{\mu b^2}{\sqrt{a^2 \delta^2 - \mu^2 b^2}}$$

As approximation for $\mu \ll \delta \leq 1$:

$$r_{min} \approx \frac{\mu b^2}{a\delta} \quad r_{max} \approx b$$

For $\mu = 0$ the velocity formulas lead to the known formula of chapter 1 for the frictionless case:

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{ga}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}}$$

For r and r_m the same relation as in chapter 1 is valid.

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{r}$

to *: The derivation of formula (2.1):

Notations:

kinetic energy = $E_{kin} = \frac{mv^2}{2}$

potential energy = $E_{pot} = mgh$ with $h = h_s \sin \alpha$ see fig.

rotational energy = $E_{rot} = \frac{Jw^2}{2}$ $J = \text{moment of inertia}$

law of conservation of energy:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jw^2}{2} = mgh$$

We assume that the body is only rolling not gliding. Then it is valid:

angular velocity = $w = \frac{v}{R}$ $R = \text{radius of the rolling body}$

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} + \frac{Jv^2}{2R^2} = mgh_s \sin \alpha$$

With transformation we get:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}}$$

Because the rolling body has the constant acceleration $b = g \sin \alpha$, there is a uniform accelerated motion. For this motion it is valid: $v^2 = 2h_s \cdot b$ transformed

to $b = \frac{v^2}{2h_s}$. Now we insert the equation of v :

$$b = \frac{2mgh_s \sin \alpha}{2h_s \cdot \left(m + \frac{J}{R^2}\right)} = \frac{mg \sin \alpha}{m + \frac{J}{R^2}}$$

Then we have the wanted formula.

Chapter 3

Inversions

3.1 Inversions to the frictionless case

We take the notation of chapter 1.

Ellipsoid of revolution:

We take the symbols of chapter 1.3. The problem is to obtain r as function of the velocity v . Here we begin with the velocity equation in chapter 1:

$$v = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{b \cdot g}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}}$$

It follows:

$$\frac{v^2}{r^2} = \frac{bg}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}$$

transformed:

$$\frac{v^4 a^2}{r^4} \cdot (a^2 - r^2) = b^2 \cdot g^2$$

We change this expression to a polynomial:

$$v^4 a^4 - v^4 a^2 \cdot r^2 = b^2 g^2 \cdot r^4$$

Normed form:

$$r^4 + \frac{v^4 a^2}{b^2 g^2} \cdot r^2 - \frac{v^4 a^4}{b^2 g^2} = 0$$

This expression is an quadratic equation to r^2 , with that:

$$r^2 = +\sqrt{\frac{v^4 a^4}{b^2 g^2} + \left(\frac{v^4 a^2}{2b^2 g^2}\right)^2} - \frac{v^4 a^2}{2b^2 g^2} \quad (3.1)$$

Now we derive a formula of r in dependence to the angular velocity w . We begin with the equation in chapter 1 of the angular velocity.

$$w^2 = \frac{bg}{a \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - r^2}}$$

transformed:

$$\sqrt{a^2 - r^2} = \frac{bg}{aw^2}$$

Solving to r :

$$\begin{aligned} r^2 &= a^2 - \left(\frac{bg}{aw^2}\right)^2 \\ r &= \sqrt{a^2 - \left(\frac{bg}{aw^2}\right)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

ball as special case of the ellipsoid of revolution:

It is also possible to view the ball as special case of the ellipsoid of revolution with the ball radius $R_k = a = b$. Specializing of (3.1) and (3.2):

$$\begin{aligned} r(v)^2 &= +\sqrt{\frac{v^4 R_k^2}{g^2} + \left(\frac{v^4}{2g^2}\right)^2} - \frac{v^4}{2g^2} \\ r &= \sqrt{R_k^2 - \left(\frac{g}{w^2}\right)^2} \end{aligned}$$

Hyperboloid:

We take the notations of chapter 1.6. Now we try to get the radius r with the velocity v , equation of chapter 1:

$$v = \sqrt{gr \cdot \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}} = r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{ag}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}}$$

transformed:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{v^2}{r^2} &= \frac{ag}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}} \\ v^4 b^2 \cdot (b^2 + r^2) &= a^2 g^2 r^4 \end{aligned}$$

multiplying out:

$$v^4 b^4 + v^4 b^2 r^2 = a^2 g^2 r^4$$

Normed form:

$$r^4 - \frac{v^4 b^2}{a^2 g^2} \cdot r^2 - \frac{v^4 b^4}{a^2 g^2} = 0$$

This expression is an quadratic equation of r^2 .

$$r^2 = +\sqrt{\frac{v^4 b^4}{a^2 g^2} + \left(\frac{v^4 b^2}{2a^2 g^2}\right)^2} + \frac{v^4 b^2}{2a^2 g^2}$$

Determination of r with the angular velocity w :

$$w = \sqrt{\frac{ag}{b \cdot \sqrt{b^2 + r^2}}}$$

Transformation:

$$\sqrt{b^2 + r^2} = \frac{ag}{bw^2}$$

solved to r :

$$r = \sqrt{\left(\frac{ag}{bw^2}\right)^2 - b^2}$$

3.2 Inversions of the friction case

We take the notation of chapter 2.1 - 2.6. If we solve the formula of the maximum velocity to the radius r , we get formulas of r_{min} . One solving of the minimum velocity formula to r leads to an expression of r_{max} . At the cone of revolution we get:

$$r_{min} = \frac{(\delta \tan \alpha - \mu) \cdot v^2}{g \cdot (\delta + \tan \alpha \cdot \mu)} \quad r_{max} = \frac{(\mu + \delta \tan \alpha) \cdot v^2}{g \cdot (\delta - \mu \tan \alpha)}$$

At the paraboloid the solving to r is more complicated. The solving leads with the help of an quadratic equation of r to the following expressions:

$$r_{min} = +\sqrt{\left(\frac{2f\mu g + \mu v^2}{2\delta g}\right)^2 + \frac{2fv^2}{g} - \frac{2f\mu g + \mu v^2}{2\delta g}}$$

$$r_{max} = +\sqrt{\left(\frac{2f\mu g + \mu v^2}{2g\delta}\right)^2 + \frac{2fv^2}{g} + \frac{2f\mu g + \mu v^2}{2g\delta}}$$

We must choose the positive root, because with a negative root the solutions are negativ, too.

At the ellipsoid and the hyperboloid we can do such solvings to r , too. We then get polynomials of degree 4 in r , which can still be solve exactly.

The formulas of velocities and angular velocities at orbits on the rotation body's shell can be written as a function of h (at the ellipsoid with the height angle

γ , too). At all special rotation bodies $r = f(h)$ can be inserted. At the general rotation body we must derive the case with h again. (From these equation we can perhaps prove the special formulas again.) For the insertions of $v, w = f(r)$ to $v, w = f(h)$ are valid:

$$x = r, y = h$$

$$\text{for ellipsoid: } \frac{r^2}{a^2} + \frac{h^2}{b^2} = 1 \quad (a \leq b) \text{ or } (a \geq b)$$

$$\text{for balls: } r^2 + h^2 = R_K^2$$

$$\text{for hyperboloids: } \frac{h^2}{a^2} - \frac{r^2}{b^2} = 1$$

$$\text{for paraboloids: } r^2 = 4hf$$

$$\text{for cones of revolution: } h = r \cdot (\tan \alpha)^{-1}$$

Bibliography

- [1] Bruno Assmann "Technische Mechanik" volume 1 Oldenbourg Verlag
12.edition Munich 1991
- [2] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition VEB Deutscher Verlag der
Wissenschaften Berlin 1980
- [3] Arnold Sommerfeld "Mechanik" volume 1 Verlag Harri Deutsch 8.edition
Frankfort on the Main 1977